

FORMATION AND DESCRIPTION OF ECONOMIC RESOURCES IN THE SERVICE FIELD

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Abstract. In this article, it is explained scientifically and theoretically that the service sector is expanding in the world and that the efficiency of service enterprises in our country is considered more efficient than production, because the initial activity in the service sector requires less investment and the turnover rate of financial funds is high.

Key words: service industry, use of economic resources, classification of economic resources, integration in the service industry, limited resources.

The development of the service sector in the world, improving the methods of evaluating the efficiency of the use of economic resources in enterprises, modernizing service processes, ensuring the competitiveness of services, material incentives for workers in the sector, increasing the quality of service, developing a system for ensuring the competence of labor resources, social- the research of scientific problems in areas such as increasing economic efficiency is gaining importance.

The expansion of the service economy in the world has its effect on the changes in the composition of the gross domestic product of the countries based on the developed market economy. In the economically developed countries, the share of service and service sector in the gross domestic product is 65-80%, and the contribution of the funds spent on investing in science and innovative activities is 3.0% ¹. Also, more than 70.0% of employment and 40.0% of direct investments in developed countries are in the service sector ². This, in turn, shows the special importance of increasing the efficiency of the use of economic resources in service enterprises.

Today, in the process of modernization of the economy of our republic, the regular and stable economic development of the enterprises of the service sector requires the improvement of the mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of the use of economic resources, which is considered an important factor for ensuring the intensity of their economic activity. In this process, the tasks of the sector are to ensure the intensity of service related to the mechanism of increasing the efficiency of the activities of service enterprises, to increase labor productivity in

¹ <http://www.worldbank.org/eca/russian/data/>

² <http://stats.pecd.org/>

the enterprises of the sector, to achieve economical use of economic resources, to achieve the efficiency of the use of labor resources, to ensure the quality of the produced services and its effectiveness, to fully satisfy the needs of service consumers. is one of its own problems. At the same time, increasing the quality of services of service enterprises in the international market and increasing the export of services is the main task of the socio-economic development of our country.

Today, 80.0% of total jobs in developed countries, particularly the US economy, are contributed by service industries. 85.0% of employees working in this field are specialists with high knowledge and qualifications.

Similar trends can be seen in other countries with dormant economies. For example, 14.0% of people employed in the UK industry, 18.0% in Japan, 20.0% in Italy and Germany. According to the information presented in the "Economist" magazine, the number of people employed in US industrial production is 10.0% of the total working age population. Almost half of them are engaged in service-related activities (design, distribution of goods, financial planning, marketing, etc.) without being directly engaged in production ³.

The current development of the world economy is under the influence of cognitive (lat. "cognitio" - "knowledge", "thinking") factors and productions based on economical economy, food and biotechnology. This leads to a sharp increase in the volume of information that is required for the development and adoption of management decisions in macroeconomics. As a result, the knowledge of employees and the level of development of information and communication technologies in each country determine its progress and competitiveness ⁴.

In the conditions of the innovative development of the economy, the development of the service sector is economically effective compared to production, because the organization of initial activities in the service sector is characterized by a high turnover rate of financial funds, requiring less investment.

At the current stage of the economic development of our country, the number and quality of services are increasing. The application of the experience of developed countries has led to an increase in the demand for services. This, in turn, caused changes in the composition of the consumer market. As a result of the increase in the material well-being of some sections of the population, a new

³O sokrashchenii zanyatosti v mirovoy promyshlennosti // BIKI. 2015. No. 138 (8934), - S. 4.

⁴Abdurakhmanov Q.Kh. Labor economics: theory and practice / Textbook. Revised and supplemented 3rd edition. - T.: Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan "FAN" publishing state enterprise, 2019. - p. 548.

category of consumers with their own requirements and needs for services has emerged. Affluent consumers are in high demand for a wide range of services that enhance their lifestyle. For this reason, some service enterprises focus their activities on meeting these demands and needs of the population ⁵.

A feature common to all types of economic resources is their relative limitation and scarcity. Limited resources limit production and services along with consumption. As a result, each enterprise, country, taking into account its capabilities, gives priority to the expansion and development of each type of production of goods and services, not all at once, but selects the most necessary ones for this period, and attracts resources to them first (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Classification of economic resources⁶

Each resource has a certain effect when it is used in the service process. Resource yield has its limits. Any resource cannot be produced beyond a certain limit even if it is used wisely.

Network integration involves pooling the resource base. Each business unit that is part of integrated business structures has its own set of resources and methods of their management. Therefore, the integration of the resource base

⁵Urakov J.R. The organizational and economic mechanism of increasing the efficiency of the activities of service enterprises (in the case of Samarkand region) // diss. iqt. science. candidate. – T.: Samisi, 2011. p. 15-16

⁶Developed by the author

requires the creation of a resource management system in accordance with the goals and strategy of the development of integrated business structures, the tasks of which may include the following: the formation of the resource base in accordance with the strategy of the development of integrated business structures; focusing on the efficiency of resource use, their importance for business; rational distribution of resources between processes and individual business units; monitoring the adequacy of necessary resources; prevent the negative effects of the external environment.

The resource base is a necessary condition for the effective operation of the service enterprise, because the timely and completeness of the activity, the increase in labor productivity and the possibility of applying innovative methods of economic management depend on the provision of economic resources and their rational use. The resource base is embodied, firstly, as a source of optimal strategy formation, secondly, as a factor influencing the organization's external environment, and thirdly, as a factor determining the direction of the organization's actions. Resources are a set of funds used in the organization's economic activities, which include fixed assets, working capital and labor resources.

Resources shape the result of activity through decisions and organized business processes, that is, resources transform organizational capabilities into the achievement of organizational goals (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Movement of economic resources in an integrated business structure in the service sector⁷

Basic means - means of labor repeatedly involved in the production process; transfers its value to the created product, goods, work, service in installments; does not change its natural-material form. Sources of formation of the main means of the enterprise: own and equivalent funds-authorized capital, depreciation deductions, part of the profit directed to the financing of capital investments; budget allocations; Debt funds are long-term loans from banks, but this applies only to capital investments in projects with a high level of profitability.

Circulating means are the means of production that carry out single economic circulation, transfer their value completely to the finished product or the provided service, and constantly change their form during the production process. According to the economic content and composition, working capital is divided into reserves, cash, receivables and other types of funds (non-monetary forms, securities).

Labor resources - the total number of employees employed in the enterprise - represents the part of the population that is employed or can work in economic sectors and industries. Labor resources are fundamentally different from all other types of enterprise resources, because they are an active part of resources and have leading importance in production.

The resource structure of enterprises in the service sector differs from that of industrial enterprises. For example, trade in enterprises work expenses share industry to enterprises relatively low. That's it to emphasize should be, the main, circulation funds and labor resources with one in line information and intellectual resources too modern in the circumstances important importance occupation It 's delicious .

In our opinion, it is economical to resources has been demand enterprise of activity to the size of, that's it of resources is prepared goods or to products has been demand, instead of clicker and filler resources for the price and another to factors depend Resources certain properties to e : mobility, combination, alternative and complexity .

⁷Developed by the author

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